

Gamma-Ray Burst Light Curve Reconstruction using Bidirectional-LSTM

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Gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) are intense phenomena that release copious amounts of gamma rays in seconds. Investigating these transient events is paramount in cosmological research because they originate from sources located at considerable redshifts. To effectively conduct such research, it is imperative to establish a connection between the observable characteristics of GRBs while minimizing uncertainty. Hence, it becomes essential to comprehensively depict the general GRB light curve (LC) to facilitate these studies. Nevertheless, the irregular spacing of observations and significant gaps in the LC, often stemming from various unavoidable factors, pose considerable challenges in characterizing GRBs. Consequently, the task of categorizing GRB LCs remains a formidable endeavor. This study introduces an innovative approach employing bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) to reconstruct gamma-ray burst (GRB) light curves. Our experimental results demonstrate that the BiLSTM approach surpasses traditional methods in performance, yielding smoother and more authentic reconstructions of GRBs.

1 Introduction

Gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) are high-redshift astronomical phenomena emitting radiation across multiple wavelengths, including gamma rays, X-rays, visible light, and radio waves. They are of great interest due to their extreme brightness and can be observed over vast cosmic distances. The Neil Gehrels Swift Observatory (Swift) has been instrumental in studying GRBs, capturing their variations in redshift, luminosity, and duration.

GRBs are commonly classified into two categories: long GRBs (LGRBs) and short GRBs (SGRBs) based on the duration parameter T_{90} . LGRBs typically last for more than 2 seconds, while SGRBs have T_{90} values less than or equal to 2 seconds [1–3]. However, studying GRBs presents challenges, including the absence of a comprehensive classification system, incomplete redshift data, and gaps in the recorded light curves

(LCs). This study addresses one of these challenges by focusing on resolving temporal gaps in GRB LCs [4]. Swift [5] has been crucial in observing GRB temporal properties, with its Burst Alert Telescope (BAT) detecting prompt emission and subsequent observations using X-ray (XRT) and Ultra-Violet (UVOT) telescopes. Swift has documented over 1000 GRBs in its first 15 years of operation [6]. Many GRB light curves exhibit unique features, such as rapid declines, flares, plateaus, and gradual declines, making them essential for studying GRB physics and cosmology [7].

Temporal gaps in LCs, caused by various factors, hinder the accurate characterization of GRBs. To overcome this challenge, this study proposes a Bidirectional LSTM model for GRB LC reconstruction, offering a more versatile and accurate approach than existing classical methods.

Bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) networks [8–14] have proven effective in time series analysis, especially for capturing long-term dependencies. They process input sequences in both forward and backward directions, allowing them to understand and predict sequential patterns comprehensively. This approach improves the overall density distribution of GRB LCs across time, enhancing their utility as standard candles and for theoretical modeling. In summary, GRBs are intriguing astronomical phenomena with various characteristics, and this study addresses the challenge of temporal gaps in their light curves using a BiLSTM-based reconstruction approach.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data Collection and Pre-processing

We use GRB light-curve data from four distinct categories: Good GRBs, Break Bump GRBs (with single and double breaks), and Bump Flares GRBs [4]. These datasets include error values for the parameters. Typically, these GRB light curves contain a limited number

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Table 1: Default size of Hyperparameters used while training our Bi-LSTM framework.

Hyperparameter	Default Size
Batch Size	900 or above
Maximum Number of Batches	3
Minimum Number of Batches	1

of data points (approximately 50 to 100). This scarcity of data poses a challenge for reconstructing complete light curves since it may not be sufficient for effective training.

To address this challenge, we employ a two-phase upsampling approach. In the first phase, we arrange the dataset chronologically to establish a proper time sequence. We then apply our BiLSTM model to the original dataset to capture the underlying patterns between the data points. Using these learned patterns, we upsample the dataset by adding ten new data points between each pair of adjacent data points from the original dataset. This augmentation is done in the original scale to minimize errors and maintain clarity in capturing both positive and negative fluctuations, which is crucial for transient events like GRBs. To address the issue of dealing with purely logarithmic scales that only allow positive values, we transform the data into a symmetric logarithmic scale using the mathematical function: $F(x) = \ln\left(\frac{x}{a}\right) + 1$, where a represents the minimum flux value and x represents the flux values. This transformation enhances the training performance of our BiLSTM model and improves predictions for missing sections of the light curve. Next, we create multiple batches, with the batch size as a parameter, to analyze the impact of batch size on the model's training. Through experimentation, we determined the optimal batch size to be 900 or above (see Table 1). Each of these batches is upsampled to provide an adequate number of data points for training. To prevent duplication of data points across batches, we segregate the batches before upsampling.

2.2 Model Architecture

We propose a multi-BiLSTM framework consisting of four BiLSTM layers and a dense layer for mapping learned representations to predictions. Unlike a single BiLSTM layer, our architecture utilizes multiple BiLSTM models, each trained on distinct time intervals of the GRB LCs. These time intervals are spread across multiple batches, and each batch is trained with one Bi-LSTM model. The number of batches used for training is between 1 and 3, inclusive. Hence, our architecture combines multiple Bi-LSTM models for predicting flux values. This localized fitting approach focuses on specific data regions, making it superior for pre-

dicting flux values in various GRB classes. Each layer has 100 hidden units. To address gradient noise due to batch-wise training on upsampled data, we employ the Adam Optimizer. ReLU activation functions in the dense layers enable the model to learn non-linear dependencies between flux and time.

The model's uniqueness is observed in the approach of its predictions. Previous models, like the Broken Power Law (BPL) model [4], assume that a simple mathematical function can accurately describe the light curve with a few parameters. However, GRB light curves can exhibit complex and diverse behaviour, which a BPL may not be able to capture fully. Moreover, GRB light curves contain intricate features and variations at short timescales, which may be challenging to represent accurately with the Broken Power Law model. In contrast, the Bidirectional LSTM model captures complex temporal patterns in the light curve data more flexibly. Firstly, it can learn and model the dependencies between different time steps, enabling a more accurate representation of the underlying behaviour. Secondly, it can effectively model the missing GRB points in the light curve.

2.3 Training and Validation

Our method is implemented using Keras and TensorFlow libraries. The training utilizes an upsampled GRB dataset, with each GRB undergoing individual training and reconstruction. The dataset is split into 70% training and 30% validation subsets for hyperparameter tuning. The training process for the BiLSTM model involves bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) neural networks, which capture information from past and future sequences. Forward and backward LSTMs process input sequences in their respective directions, with outputs combined at each time step. The forward LSTM processes from $t = 1$ to $t = T$, while the backward LSTM processes in reverse order. Training consists of 100 iterations with batch size 15, employing early stopping to enhance efficiency. The loss metric used is Mean Square Error (MSE) [15], quantifying the squared deviations between observed and expected values. MSE helps prevent overfitting, ensuring the model generalizes well to new data. The training process is repeated to optimize performance, considering the challenges posed by tracking light curve direction and equipment interference.

3 Results

We propose an algorithm for precise Light Curve Reconstruction (LCR) that emphasizes small times-

Figure 1: Light Curves of Various Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs) with Different Temporal Features

Table 2: Comparing % Flux Uncertainty Reduction (After Reconstruction) for Good Category GRBs: Our BiLSTM vs. W07, (W07+GP), BPL, (BPL+GP) Models

GRB ID	%EF (Bi-LSTM)	%EF (W07)	%EF (W07+GP)	%EF (BPL)	%EF (BPL+GP)
050318	-14.19	-24.05	-27.68	-23.11	-24.84
050416A	-23.07	-33.54	-34.04	-22.5	-20.55
050607	-11.11	-22.79	-19.62	-11.78	-6.18
050712	-15.78	-24.96	-36.97	-28.48	-31.16
050713A	-12.50	-14.31	-15.29	-18.89	-17.92
050822	-10.50	-35.46	-33.14	-14.2	-10.96
050824	-8.50	-38.45	-37.19	-30.63	-29.54
050826	-5.88	-15.21	-36.64	-35.02	-10
050915B	-20.0	-34.25	-37.46	-35.02	-12.3
051016A	-5.80	-28.49	-17.02	-48.27	-36.85
051109A	-9.23	-58.89	-49.53	-24.17	-18.84
051221A	-7.77	-58.89	-36.64	-23.82	-27.45
060105	-22.72	-30.58	-20.31	-34.29	-29.55
060108	-4.34	-14.1	-28.84	-25.54	-19.39
060109	-5.85	-45.09	-44.23	-9.85	-1
060124	-13.80	-29.34	-34.36	-16.28	-14.13
060218	-4.45	-63	-65.62	-21.99	-15.08
060306	-18.1	-28.7	-26.66	-78.27	-79.69
060418	-6.66	-32.48	-37.74	-57.75	-55.91
060421	-10.71	-40.58	-20.75	-59.92	-46.22

Table 3: Table showing Error Fraction and % decrease in uncertainty over flux values after reconstruction of GRB LCs with our BiLSTM model for GRBs belonging to the Bump Flare, Break Bump (with single break), and Break Bump (with double break) category.

GRB ID	EF (Bi-LSTM)	EF (Bi-LSTM RC)
050803	0.013	-23.52
140304A	0.009	-30.76
140713A	0.007	-30.0
190607B	0.0112	-7.96
060206	0.013	-23.52
141005A	0.019	-19.83
141221A	0.0153	-8.92
140709A	0.006	-45.45
050712	0.005	-11.83
060219	0.015	-22.68
060923C	0.008	-38.67
070129	0.006	-25.68

tamp variations, enhancing accuracy and applicability across diverse Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs). Using Bidirectional-LSTM for LCR on GRBs, we reduce flux uncertainties compared to [4]. We quantify the decrease in flux uncertainty with the error fraction ($EF_{\log_{10}F_a}$):

$$EF_{\log_{10}F_a} = \left| \frac{\Delta \log_{10}F_a}{\log_{10}F_a} \right|$$

For LCR with Gaussian Process, we previously employed a 95% confidence interval. The % decrease in flux uncertainty for four models (W07, BPL, W07 + GP, and BPL + GP) is calculated as:

$$\%DEC = \frac{|EF_X^{After}| - |EF_X^{Before}|}{|EF_X^{Before}|} \times 100$$

Our analysis reveals that our Bidirectional LSTM model yields lower % decrease in flux uncertainty compared to the W07, BPL, (W07 + GP) model (see Table 2). Conversely, for the (BPL + GP) model (see Table 2), our Bidirectional LSTM exhibits a higher decrease in flux uncertainty for three GRBs (GRB050607, GRB050915B, and 060109).

4 Discussion and Conclusion

GRB light curve monitoring is vital for understanding collimated jets, energy demands, and cosmology. We introduce a BiLSTM model, overcoming limitations of existing models like the Willingale function [16] and prior LCR studies [4]. Our approach enhances accuracy by focusing on local data regions, handles multi-wavelength data, and identifies plateau features, shedding light on progenitor processes, redshift, classification, and explosion dynamics. This precision aids cos-

mological research, refining distance measurements and parameters.

Despite its advantages, our BiLSTM model has limitations, such as variable-length inputs, data preprocessing challenges, and limited window contents. Future work will explore other deep-learning models for GRB light curve reconstruction. We also observed that models performed best with a batch size between 1 and 3 across all GRB categories. In data preprocessing, we created time sequences with a fixed parameter of 1, corresponding to a single point. Predictions were collected and converted back to the original scale from symlog for visualization.

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